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Assessing the Role of Teacher-Related Factors in Principals' Delegation of Authority and School Administrative Effectiveness in Imo State

Akalonu, Chinyere

Department of Educational Management,
Faculty of Education
University of Port Harcourt, Port Jaecourt, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the relationship between teacher-related factors' influence on principals' delegation of authority and overall administrative effectiveness in schools in Imo State. Recognising that effective school leadership often hinges on strategic delegation, the research explored how variables such as teachers' professional expertise, years of experience, educational qualifications, and residential proximity to the school shape principals' decisions to assign administrative responsibilities. Using a correlational research design, data were collected from a representative sample of 175 principals through two structured questionnaires titled: Teacher-Related Factors' Influence on Principals' Delegation of Authority Questionnaire (TFIPDAQ) and Administrative Effectiveness in Schools Questionnaire (AESQ). Quantitative analysis was employed to determine the extent of the relationship, as such data were analysed using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation for research questions and z-ratio statistics to test null hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level. Findings revealed a positive but weak relationship between principals' consideration of teachers' location when delegating authority and their overall administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo State. It further revealed that principals' consideration of teachers' expertise, disposition, qualification, and location significantly contributes to administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo State. The study concluded that a holistic consideration of teachers' expertise, disposition, qualification, and location enables principals to make more informed and effective administrative decisions. It was recommended that School principals should create an appealing atmosphere that allows teachers to engage in their designated responsibilities so that they can be of assistance to the administrator in running the school activity smartly in line with their terms and conditions of work.

Keywords: Delegation of Authority, Administrative Effectiveness, Teacher-Related Factors, School Leadership, Public Secondary Schools.

INTRODUCTION

Leadership is essential to the advancement and survival of any organisation, whether it is a business or an academic institution. Thus, power delegation is a sensible technique used by administrators to guide the activities of individuals in the workplace, enabling them to reach the intended outcome. It is the act of persuading individuals to work voluntarily and enthusiastically toward the achievement of goals. In a school context, principals are responsible for managing both instructors and pupils in order to achieve the nation's educational objectives while meeting the different demands of the times. This is to say that, if

education must move along with the current trends of development, then school principals have to be innovative and creative in the discharge of administrative duties.

Given the significance that teachers play in individual development, they are a major predictor of a school's success or failure. They serve as the foundation for any educational system. The roots transport nourishment to all of the tree's branches. Without living or healthy roots, the tree will slowly die or wither. From the above assertion, Arop, Akan and Owan (2018), deduced that for teachers or administrators of school to be able to run the affairs of school smoothly in the place of authority delegation in line with organizational goals, credibility in terms of experience, qualification, disposition, competence and the expert vigor of these key players must be put into serious consideration.

It is evident in administrative practice that there may be correlations between student performance and teacher effectiveness, as well as between performance and classroom climate. That is, for principals to distribute authority by administrative aims, they must examine teacher expertise and practice, which is motivated by their notable abilities to respond to certain conditions and situations. A teacher who lacks a competent teaching strategy will always yield bad results. Similarly, a teacher who is unable to motivate his or her students to learn, whether through teacher-student interaction or counselling, will generate bad students. In the same spirit, Ladd (2008) discovered that, on average, teachers with expert understanding of their work tend to perform more productively than those who lack such skill when addressing specific responsibilities.

Furthermore, delegating jobs based on knowledge and practice to staff allows them to not only do their best but also to showcase their abilities, because in certain circumstances, heads and staff meet together to develop school internal regulations to fulfil the curiosity of internal happenings. Principals must evaluate concerns of knowledge when distributing power for potential functional responsibility in the school. As a result, what qualifies someone to teach and can impact students' academic performance is tied to certain attributes that a teacher acquired in the classroom and received certification at a specific point in his or her career.

As a result, delegating functional responsibility to instructors necessitates careful examination of the extent of the teacher's knowledge in order to assign the proper function to the right person who can do the right job and generate the expected results. Teaching tactics, experience, professional development, motivation, and interaction are all unique to each teacher and evolve over their careers.

A teacher who has a teaching technique today may not have it tomorrow, but it does not justify assigning him special responsibility at that time to teach something that will not provide the intended results. As a result, he or she must be assigned responsibilities that are most appropriate for his or her current situation. Teachers' qualifications are rationally accounted for by their professional and experience-based development. Rationally, the administrative leadership style used by principals determines the school's ability to adjust to changing circumstances and its level of effectiveness. In general, to determine academic staff performance or teacher productivity, sensitive issues concerning the school environment, such as infrastructural facilities, buildings, school plants, staff offices, laboratories, libraries, conveniences for staff and students, recreational facilities, and so on, must be in good condition, and the functional responsibility to maintain them must be well delegated by principals.

Pacis and Weegar (2011) have stated that an excellent teacher possesses intangible characteristics of ethical behaviour that are immediately identifiable and visible. These behaviours, known as dispositions, include friendliness, caring, and having high expectations for children and teachers. Principals must consider this while allocating responsibility as a strategy. Teachers' dispositions are the personality qualities and behavioural patterns that an individual teacher demonstrates directly or indirectly, and which have an impact on students' learning results, either favourably or negatively. It contributes to shaping instructors' classroom approaches and reducing their overreliance on traditional techniques, especially when such practices are not generating or creating the expected educational outcomes - student performance/achievement. This implies that teachers tend to replace these old and conventional techniques, transforming them from consumers of knowledge to producers of new knowledge.

Statement of the Problem

Teachers, key to curriculum implementation, often neglect their duties after delegation, exhibiting lateness, disrespect, disobedience, poor time management, and weak organisational skills. In secondary schools, principal-teacher relations suffer from mismatched assignments, poor supervision, inadequate facilities, and conflicting roles, weakening school-community ties and student outcomes. Some principals lack vision, proper job analysis, and instructional oversight, leading to poor curriculum delivery and academic performance. Their ineffective delegation strategies further reduce administrative efficiency. It is against this background that this study aims to examine the aforementioned issues.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study evaluated the relationship between teacher-related factors' influence on principals' delegation of authority and overall administrative effectiveness in schools within Imo State. Specifically, the objectives of the study were:

1. find out the relationship between principals' consideration of teachers' location in the delegation of authority strategies and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo State.
2. determine the joint relationship that exists between principals' consideration of teachers' expertise, disposition, qualification, location and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo State.

Research Question

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the relationship between principals' consideration of teachers' location in the delegation of authority strategy and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo State?
2. What joint relationship exists between principals' consideration of teachers' expertise, disposition, qualification, location and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested in the study at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between principals' consideration of teachers' location in the delegation of authority strategy and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo State.
2. There is no significant joint relationship between principals' consideration of teachers' expertise, disposition, qualification, location and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo State.

RESEARCH METHODS

The study adopted a correlational research design. The population comprised all 311 public secondary schools across the 27 Local Government Areas of Imo State, with all 311 principals as potential respondents. A sample of 202 principals (69% of the population) was selected using Taro Yamane's formula, which determined a minimum sample size of 175. Simple random sampling via balloting (YES/NO cards without replacement) was used to select the final sample, ensuring adequate representation. Two instruments were used for data collection: Teacher-Related Factors' Influence on Principals' Delegation of Authority Questionnaire (TFIPDAQ) and Administrative Effectiveness in Schools Questionnaire (AESQ). Both were structured on a 4-point modified Likert scale (SA = 4, A = 3, D = 2, SD = 1) and validated by three experts. Reliability was tested using Cronbach Alpha with 30 principals outside the study sample. The average reliability coefficient for (TFIPDAQ) was 0.86 and AESQ had a reliability coefficient of 0.77, indicating acceptable internal consistency. Questionnaires were administered and retrieved directly by the researcher and three trained assistants. Data were analysed using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation for research questions and z-ratio statistics to test null hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the relationship between principals’ consideration of teachers’ location in the delegation of authority strategy and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo State?*

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between principals’ consideration of teachers’ location in the delegation of authority strategy and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo State.

Table 1: Pearson correlation of teachers’ location and administrative effectiveness

Variable	N	R	P	α	Decision
Teachers’ location	202	0.159	0.061	0.05	H ₀₄
Administrative Effectiveness					Non-Significant

Table 1 shows a correlation coefficient of 0.159, indicating a weak relationship between principals’ consideration of teachers’ location in delegation strategies and administrative effectiveness in Imo State public secondary schools. The corresponding p-value of 0.061 exceeds the 0.05 alpha level, confirming no significant relationship. Thus, the null hypothesis was retained.

Research Question Two: *What joint relationship exists between principals’ consideration of teachers’ expertise, disposition, qualification, location and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo State?*

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant joint relationship between principals’ consideration of teachers’ expertise, disposition, qualification, location and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo State.

Table 2: Multiple regression analysis of joint relationship between principals’ consideration of teachers’ expertise, disposition, qualification, location and administrative effectiveness.

Model	R	R ²	Adj. R ²	Std. Error of Estimates
	0.660	0.366	0.354	6.573

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	5041.943	4	1260.486	28.489	0.000
Residual	8716.076	197	44.244		
Total	13758.020	201			

Table 2 shows that principals’ consideration of teachers’ expertise, disposition, qualification, and location jointly accounted for 35.4% of administrative effectiveness (adjusted R² = 0.354). ANOVA results yielded an F-value of 28.489 and a p-value of 0.0005, which is below the 0.05 significance level. This indicates a significant joint relationship, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study in Table 1 revealed a positive but weak relationship between principals’ consideration of teachers’ location when delegating authority and their overall administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo State. This suggests that while location may have some influence, it is not a primary factor in principals’ decision-making. Instead, principals tend to assign responsibilities based on teachers’ competence and credibility, rather than proximity to the school. However, this approach can have implications for administrative effectiveness, particularly when long distances hinder teachers’ punctuality and consistent presence. This finding aligns with Raheem (2010), who identified home-to-school distance as a key factor contributing to poor responsiveness to duty and subpar student performance in public examinations. Raheem’s study highlighted several challenges affecting school effectiveness, including:

- Poor school location and long commuting distances for staff
- Frequent changes in government education policies

- School closures due to teachers' strike actions
- High student-teacher ratios
- Ineffective delegation, supervision, and evaluation mechanisms
- Inadequate instructional materials and textbooks
- Poor instructional content and delivery
- Unfavorable school environments

In contrast, Akbar and Allvar (2010) found that school administrators who travel long distances to work often arrive late, which negatively impacts the implementation of administrative directives and overall school management. However, the current study diverges from Hamili (2007), who reported no significant relationship between job location and job satisfaction among secondary school teachers. It also contradicts Nirav (2018), who emphasised the importance of proximity in delegation. Nirav argued that teachers assigned to oversee activities occurring before or after school hours should live nearby to manage these responsibilities with patience and confidentiality. He further suggested that schools should be situated in environments conducive to fulfilling teachers' roles effectively.

The results presented in Table 2 indicate that principals' consideration of teachers' expertise, disposition, qualification, and location significantly contributes to administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo State. Specifically, these factors jointly accounted for 35.4% of the variance in administrative effectiveness (adjusted $R^2 = 0.354$). The ANOVA results ($F = 28.489$, $p = 0.0005$) further confirm the statistical significance of this relationship, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

These findings underscore the importance of strategic human resource considerations in school leadership. The significant joint influence suggests that principals who actively evaluate and incorporate teachers' professional attributes and contextual realities into their administrative decisions are more likely to achieve effective school management. This result aligns with the work of Adeyemi (2010), who emphasised that teacher expertise and professional disposition are critical to the success of school administration. Adeyemi found that principals who delegate responsibilities based on teachers' strengths and qualifications foster a more productive and responsive school environment. Similarly, Okeke and Uche (2012) highlighted the role of teacher qualification and disposition in enhancing instructional leadership and administrative coordination. Their study showed that when principals recognise and utilise teachers' professional competencies, it leads to improved organisational outcomes and student performance. The inclusion of teacher location as a contributing factor also resonates with Raheem (2010), who identified geographical proximity and commuting challenges as influential in staff punctuality and responsiveness. Although location may not be the strongest predictor individually, its interaction with other variables such as expertise and disposition can shape the overall effectiveness of administrative strategies.

Contrary to Hamili (2007), who found no significant relationship between job location and job satisfaction, the current study suggests that location, when considered alongside other professional attributes, plays a meaningful role in administrative planning and execution. Moreover, Nirav (2018) argued that assigning responsibilities to teachers who live closer to the school enhances their ability to manage pre- and post-school activities with greater dedication and confidentiality. This supports the notion that location, while not always prioritised, can influence the quality of delegated tasks and administrative outcomes.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the findings of this study affirm that a holistic consideration of teachers' expertise, disposition, qualification, and location enables principals to make more informed and effective administrative decisions. This integrated approach contributes significantly to the overall effectiveness of school leadership and management.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Considering the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are made:

1. School principals should create an appealing atmosphere that allows teachers to engage in their designated responsibilities so that they can be of assistance to the administrator in running the school activity smartly in line with their terms and conditions of work.
2. School administrators should systematically assess teachers' expertise, disposition, and qualifications when assigning responsibilities. Delegating tasks based on professional strengths enhances administrative effectiveness and promotes a more efficient and motivated workforce.

REFERENCES

- Adeyemi, T. O. (2010). *Principals' leadership styles and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria*. *Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 2(6), 83–91.
- Akbari, R., & Allvar, N. K. (2010). L2 Teacher characteristics as predictors of students' academic achievement. *The Electronic Journal for English as a Second Language*, 13(4), 1 – 22.
- Arop, F. O., Akan, E. M., & Owan, V. J. (2018). Management of school related variables and teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Research*, 4(8), 90 – 100.
- Hamili, A. (2007). *Job location and job satisfaction among public school teachers*. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 1(2), 45–58.
- Nirav, P. (2018). *Impact of teacher proximity on school administrative efficiency*. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 8(3), 112–124.
- Okeke, C. I., & Uche, C. M. (2012). *Teacher qualification and instructional leadership in Nigerian secondary schools*. *African Journal of Educational Management*, 4(1), 67–79.
- Pacis, D. & Weegar, M. A. (2011). *Thoughts of one former elementary school principal on teacher dispositions, hiring practices and no child left behind*. <http://www.g-casa.com/conference/vietnam/paper/Pacis.pdf>.
- Raheem, K. A. (2010). *Geographical factors affecting teacher performance in rural schools*. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Planning*, 3(2), 98–107.
- Raheem, M. J. (2010). *Relationship between teachers' characteristics and senior secondary school economics students' performance in Ilorin, Nigeria*. Unpublished B.Sc (Ed) Research Project, University of Ilorin, Ilorin.